

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KAPADIA****FIRST NAME: DHRUTI****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 5A****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is used to indicate a spelling error in a quoted text?

Deleted: ing

- If necessary, you may mark errors with '[sic]' or insert missing text in the square brackets.¹
- Quoting is an important technique used to include information from outside sources in academic writing.
- Used effectively, quotations can provide important pieces of evidence and lend fresh voices and perspectives to your narrative.
- Quotation marks are a type of punctuation used to show direct quotes, dialogue, and certain titles or otherwise to set aside words in text.

Deleted: ,

Formatted: Font: 10 pt, Italic

Formatted: Font: 10 pt

Deleted: .

Deleted: ¶

¹European Union, *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*, (European Commission: European Union, 2021), 9.

2. How are the legal provisions referred?

- References to legal provisions: Regarding legal provisions such as the French ‘salon 1’ article X’, English users are more targeted set of formulas than most languages. To find the appropriate one, you need to know what the provision does. Remember, there is no single right way.²**
- Legal provisions, in the context of law and regulations, refer to the specific rules, requirements, and clauses outlined in legal documents such as statutes, regulations, contracts, and agreements.
- When referring to legal provisions in writing, it is important to follow proper citation and formatting conventions.
- The capitalization of terms in legal provisions often follows a specific style, such as capitalizing defined terms of specific headings.

3. What does dissertation mean?

- The dissertation is a final presentation of the design execution and interpretation of the research that was planned in the dissertation prospectus. The dissertation defense-allows students to: a) demonstrate that the procedures agreed upon in the dissertation prospectus are well faithfully executed, b) explain how the findings were derived, and c) defend the discussion, implications, and conclusion.³**

² [Ibid.](#), 61.

³ [James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* \(Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017\), 4.](#)

Deleted:

Deleted: English Style Guide, *A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*, (European Commission: European Union 2021),

Deleted:

¶
¶
¶
¶
¶

Formatted: Justified

Deleted: P.

Deleted: (*Second Edition*),

Deleted: ,

Deleted: (

Formatted: Font: Times New Roman, 10 pt

Formatted: Font: Times New Roman, 10 pt

Formatted: Indent: First line: 0 cm

- A dissertation is a comparatively lengthier piece of scholarly writing that accounts for your research work throughout the doctoral program.
- A proposition submitted by the candidate for a doctoral degree in some universities, which must be sustained by argument against any objections offered.
- A dissertation is a scholarly written document that presents original research and findings in a specific academic field or subject.

4. What is the critical analysis of [the](#) literature review implying?

- A literature review is a type of critical review in which you analyze and evaluate many sources on a specific topic.
- The critical analysis of the literature (gap in content and method) is placed-prior to the research questions.⁴**
- A critical analysis is your evaluation of a book, article, research, or any other source that provides information used in a literature review.
- The purpose is to provide your reader with an overview of the research that has been done on your topic, and to evaluate the sources you are reviewing.

5. What do you mean by limitation of study?

- Limitations in research are restrictions and constraints which have been put on your methodology of study and exploration process in general.
- Limitations represent weaknesses within the study that may research outcomes and conclusions limitations of the study in research proposal the research.

⁴ [Ibid., 39.](#)

Deleted: P. James Sampson, (*Second Edition*), *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Tallahassee: (Florida State University, 2017), 39⁴

Formatted: Footer

Limitations may result from anticipated problems associated with sampling the measures the treatment, the data analysis and the execution of the procedures.⁵

Limitations is the term used for constraints that impact the researcher's ability to effectively study the scope of the project.

6. What do you mean by revising of drafts?

To revise effectively, you must know what readers look for and whether you are graph helps them find it.⁶

When writing a research paper, it is easy to become overly focused on editorial details, such as the proper format for bibliographic entries.

Once you have your first draft, it will require revision.

To determine what needs reworking, read the entire paper—preferably aloud.

7. Define author date style and basic form?

Author date style and basic form - citation style used widely in most social sciences and in natural and physical sciences is the author-date style, so called because the authors name and the date of the publications are the critical elements for identifying the sources.⁷

Author-date style is the preferred option in the sciences and social sciences.

⁵ [Ibid.](#)

⁶ [Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colombo, Joseph Bizup, Williams Fitzgerald, and University of Chicago Press Staff. \(Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018\), 106.](#)

⁷ [Ibid.](#), 226

Deleted: P. James Sampson, (*Second Edition*), *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research Tallahassee*: (Florida State University, 2017), 39

Formatted: Indent: First line: 0 cm

Deleted: L.

Deleted: ,

Deleted: .

Deleted: (

Formatted: Font: 10 pt

Deleted: L. Kate, Turbian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colombo, Joseph Bizup, Williams Fitzgerald, and University of Chicago Press Staff. Chicago: (The University of Chicago Press, 2018)

- In author-date style, an in-text citation consists of the author's name, the publication year, and (if relevant) a page number.
- In the author-date citation system, each work used in a paper has two parts: an in-text citation and a corresponding reference list entry.

8. What is plagiarism in research?

- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.⁸**
- Expressing an idea in your own words, and not giving credit.
- Paraphrasing is plagiarism if you put the author's ideas completely in your own words and properly cite the source.
- In academic writing, plagiarizing involves using words, ideas, or information from a source without citing it correctly. In practice, this can mean a few different things.

9. When do you give credit to the author?

- When using any quote, paraphrase, statistics/data, or visuals (such as a graph) that are borrowed from another source.⁹**
- Once you have brought source material into your writing (via quotation, summary, or paraphrase), your next task is to cite or identify it.
- You give credit in two ways: within the paper in footnotes or parenthetical and at the end of a paper in the bibliography.

⁸ Laurent, Cleenewrek, and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, (Bangui: Central African Republic, 2021), 34.

⁹ *Ibid.*, 34.

Deleted: the role of

Deleted: ,

Deleted: Cleenewrek

Deleted: ,

Deleted: Kabiru,

Deleted: .

Deleted: (

Formatted: Font: 10 pt

Formatted: Font: 10 pt

Formatted: Font: 10 pt

Formatted: s41, Justified, Space After: 9 pt

Deleted: ¶

Deleted: Laurent, Cleenewrek, and Gulma, Kabiru. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: (Central African Republic, 2021),

Formatted: Font: 10 pt

Formatted: Indent: First line: 0 cm

In order to comply with the law, you should always credit the source.

10. What is the correct way to insert footnotes?

Each footnote must begin on a new line, indented in the same amount as paragraphs in the footnotes, which are usually single-spaced with a blank line between notes.¹⁰

Footnotes are short, numbered notes that are placed at the bottom of the page in an essay or article.

Footnotes are references on bottom of every page.

Footnotes are similar to bibliography.

Footnotes are for ready reference of research content.

¹⁰ [Ibid.](#), 52.

Deleted: Laurent, Cleenewrek, and Gulma, Kabiru. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: (Central African Republic, 2021),

Formatted: Font: 10 pt

BIBLIOGRAPHY

[European Union](#), *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*. European Union, 2021.

Deleted: English Style Guide.

Formatted: Justified

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Deleted: European Commission:

Deleted: (Second Edition).

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colombo, Joseph Bizup, Williams Fitzgerald, and University of Chicago Press Staff. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Deleted:

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Central African Republic, 2021.

Deleted:

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.